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ICT4CART project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research & innovation programme under grant agreement No. 768953. Content reflects only the authors' view and European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Printed on 100% recycled, chlorine-free paper using vegetable ink. Design: www.beelzeppub.com

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